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A comparative study of melting behavior of phase change material with direct fluid contact and container inclination

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ABSTRACT

Finding a low-cost method to improve the heat transfer rate in thermal energy storage (TES) is essential in the modern world. In the current research, the comparison of inclined systems, which are among the inexpensive methods, with the new combined system employing the auxiliary fluid of water is discussed. Oleic acid is selected as an unsolvable PCM in water to reuse chosen materials at the end of the melting process in more TES cycles. In the combined system, the density difference between water and PCM is utilized to enhance the melting rate of PCM by placing water on the top of PCM to make direct contact. Therefore, water, which has a heavier density than PCM, takes the place of the melted PCM at the bottom of the enclosure during the melting of PCM. At first, the inclined system is examined at seven different inclination angles to identify the energy storage rate. A mathematical model is formulated using the water-PCM system's continuity, momentum, and energy equations. Then, the melting process of the combined system is studied to compare the energy storage rate of combined and inclined systems. Comparing the combined system with the optimal case of inclined systems, the average fluid velocity is 5.44 times higher, which shows the improvement of convection. It was found that the energy storage rate of the combined system (0.299136 kW/kg) is 1.85 times higher than the inclined system (0.161983 kW/kg at the inclination of 30°). As a result, the comprehensive study of the combined system is essential in future research to replace expensive methods.

1. Introduction

The global community is increasingly interested in renewable energy due to environmental concerns associated with burning fossil fuels. Thermal energy storage is expected to overcome the existing gap between energy supplies and necessities. Much research is currently being conducted on thermal energy storage (TES) systems due to their capacity to save a tremendous amount of energy with just a small increase in temperature. In TES applications, phase change materials (PCMs) offer the most significant potential for storing thermal energy. In contrast, long-term thermal energy storage requires sophisticated techniques, complex installations, and unique materials. Some applications require high

thermal capacities and low melting points called PCMs. PCMs are now widely available for various applications because they have high thermal capacities and convenient melting points. Consequently, the concept PCMs usage is based on melting/solidification heat transfer through latent heat energy during PCM-charging/discharging.

In TES applications, PCMs are utilized to sustain reliability and efficiency in solar collectors [1], cooling systems [2], buildings [3], spacecraft [4], power plant gas turbines [5], and the food industry [6]. The low thermal conductivity of PCMs significantly restricts the melting and solidification rate during the energy storage process [7]. Throughout the past decades, countless investigations have been conducted on PCMs and improved performance methods of TES systems to increase thermal efficiency. Several techniques have been developed to improve the heat transfer rates in TES, including fins [8], porous media [9], heat exchangers [10], nanoparticles [11], and carbon nanotubes [12].

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Nomenclature

C_p	specific heat capacity, kJ/kg.K
g	gravity, m/s ²
h_{sf}	latent heat, kJ/kg
ΔH	latent heat in an instant, kJ/kg
k	thermal conductivity, W/m.K
N	number of materials
P	pressure, Pa
T	temperature, °C
t	time, s
u	velocity component in horizontal direction, m/s
v	velocity component in vertical direction, m/s

Greek Symbols

α	void fraction
β	thermal expansion, 1/K
Γ	mass flux, kg/m ² .s
γ	liquid fraction
μ	dynamic viscosity, kg/m.s
ρ	density, kg/m ³

Subscripts

k	indicator of materials
l	liquid
m	melting
s	solid

Many researchers have used thermal enhancement methods to improve TES systems' performance. A numerical study by Nakhchi and Esfahani [13] examined a TES system with stepped fins on the heated side. Results demonstrated that stepped fins melt faster than horizontal fins in all tests. At 800 and 3600 s, downward-stepped fins could enhance melting by 56.3% and 65.5%, respectively, compared to conventional horizontal fins. Farahani et al. [14] investigated an energy storage system with strip fins that uses nanoparticles and magnetic fields to enhance PCM melting. In comparison to the one without fins, the new arrangement reduces PCM melting time by 51%. Chen et al. [15] proposed a novel lattice Boltzmann model for porous PCM in a cylindrical heat exchanger to evaluate the effect of natural convection on the melting process. The results showed that natural convection could accelerate PCM melting by up to 10%. Sheikholeslami and Mahian [16] modeled the solidification rate of PCM as a result of adding both inorganic nanoparticles and a magnetic field. According to the results, adding nanoparticles to PCM with volume fractions up to 4% decreases solidification time by 14%. Further, the obtained results suggest that magnetic fields can be used to accelerate solidification in TES systems. Also, the additive of nanoparticles can increase the impact of magnetic fields. Zou et al. [17] experimentally improved the performance of a lithium-ion power battery thermal management system using multi-walled carbon nanotubes and graphene combined with PCM. The composite PCM reduced the temperature rate by 63.3% compared with pure PCM. However, most heat transfer improvement methods have high costs, including the cost of construction and preparation. Therefore, the ways that are easier to access and less expensive can be more effective.

It has been shown in numerous experimental and numerical studies that buoyancy-driven convection heat transfer plays a vital role during PCM melting in different configurations. In some studies, researchers have examined the effect of inclining the enclosure on the convection flow pattern and on PCM melting behavior. Sharifi et al. [18] examined the effects of inclination during exterior melting from a warmed rod in a three-dimensional cylindrical enclosure. Temporal changes in the solid-liquid interface and temperature distribution in the molten PCM were significantly affected by even a slight inclination of the enclosure. An experiment was conducted by Kamkari et al. [19] to investigate the dy-

namical thermal behavior of PCMs melting at different inclination angles in a rectangular enclosure using Lauric acid as a PCM. In the experimental investigations, hot walls were heated to 55, 60, and 70 °C with inclination angles of 0°, 45°, and 90°. With a decrease from 90° to 0° in the inclination angle, chaotic flow patterns appear in the enclosure, and convection flows increase. Solid-liquid interface lines in the horizontally inclined enclosure become wavy whenever melting commences, implying the appearance of Benard convection cells. Also, as the hot wall temperature is the same, decreasing of inclination angle causes a significant improvement in heat transfer to the PCM. As a result, compared to vertical enclosures, horizontal enclosures have a greater heat transfer enhancement ratio. Dai et al. [20] numerically studied the melting process of PCM in a rectangular enclosure heated from various sides using the enthalpy-based lattice Boltzmann method. The impact of different inclinations between the heat flux and gravity on the melting process is investigated. Results demonstrated that increasing the inclination of the enclosure increases the mean dimensionless velocity was improved. In addition, natural heat transfer inside the enclosure evolves more intensively, and the melting rate improvement becomes faster. Liu et al. [21] have numerically evaluated molten PCM's natural convective heat transfer characteristics in an inclined enclosure with forced convection and constant heat flux boundary conditions. Increasing the number of dimensionless variables, including Reynolds numbers, Rayleigh numbers, inclination angles, and aspect ratios, are evaluated to quantify the heat transfer performance of molten PCM. These parameters result in changes to the heat transfer efficiency of 10.76%, 36.53%, 20.34%, and 28.45%, respectively.

At first, Favakeh et al. [22] tried to improve the performance of a TES system by using two PCMs with different configurations. Nevertheless, using one PCM with a higher latent heat could be more practical than two PCMs. Accordingly, instead of a double PCMs system, an insoluble auxiliary fluid can be employed in direct contact with a phase change material to improve the performance of the TES system. This enhancement technique has been developed based on the density difference between used materials. An auxiliary fluid with a higher density than PCM in the designed TES system is initially placed above the PCM. During the melting, the PCM moves upward due to its lower density, and the auxiliary fluid replaces its region. Accordingly, Mehrjardi et al. [23] studied the effect of the sinusoidal warmed wall on the melting process of various PCMs to prove the improvement intensity of using auxiliary fluid compared with a simple PCM system. However, the advantage of using auxiliary fluid to improve the melting of PCM compared to other enhancement methods is not examined previously. In addition, it is investigating an enclosure exposed to a warm wall with a constant temperature that is preferred over the spatial sinusoidal temperature.

In the current research, the performance of a novel TES system using water as an auxiliary fluid, placing the upper half of the enclosure in direct contact with oleic acid as a PCM, is compared with the inclined enclosure method to demonstrate the superiority of the combined method. The novelty of using combined method is based on using the density difference between PCM and water, which improves the melting process of PCM. The inclined enclosure containing PCM is investigated at different inclinations to find the maximum energy storage improvement. Then, a system that includes 50% water and 50% oleic acid is studied, while water with a higher density is placed on oleic acid. Finally, the most effective method is determined according to the energy stored in the TES system. Both methods are more affordable to improve heat transfer than enhancement methods such as nanoparticles and fins.

2. Physical and mathematical model

2.1. Model description

An inclined rectangular enclosure filled with PCM and designed TES system to simulate auxiliary fluid and PCM in direct contact with each other are schematically shown in Fig. 1. There is one wall in the encl-

Fig. 1. The schematic of (a) inclined enclosure and (b) combined TES system.

sure that is heated isothermally at 60°C , and the other walls are adiabatic. Meanwhile, the walls are also enforced with a no-slip boundary condition. First, different inclination angles, including 0° , 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° , and 90° , are examined for a more detailed energy storage analysis in the simple TES system. Then, a combined TES system consisting of 50% water and 50% oleic acid is investigated to compare its energy storage potential with the simple system. In order to take advantage of the displacement between auxiliary fluid and PCM caused by density differences, auxiliary fluid is positioned on top of PCM in the enclosure, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

There are many benefits associated with using water as an auxiliary fluid since it is a readily accessible and affordable material. PCM must be insoluble in the auxiliary fluid to employ the designed TES system for more cycles. In this regard, choosing a suitable PCM is one of the most crucial components of the TES system. Oleic acid, an organic PCMs insoluble in water, has low thermal conductivity, congruent melting, and high latent heat of fusion. The thermophysical properties of water and oleic acid are described in Table 1. Also, the contact angle between water and oleic acid at side walls to use wall adhesion in simulations

is calculated at 30° based on the experimental results of Khademi et al. [24].

2.2. Mathematical formulation

In the case of liquid PCM and water, Newtonian principles and incompressible laminar flow are assumed. Also, an approximation of Boussinesq is used in modeling volumetric changes. Thermophysical properties remain constant during the melting process in both solid and liquid states. In addition, a model of melting in the enclosure is based on the enthalpy-porosity relationship [29]. Simulated domains are distinguished as porous zones based on the liquid fraction (γ), which changes between 0 and 1 to indicate porosity. The governing equations, which include continuity, momentum, and energy equations, are as follows [30]:

Continuity:

$$\frac{\partial(\alpha_k \rho_k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\alpha_k \rho_k u_k)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\alpha_k \rho_k v_k)}{\partial y} = \Gamma_k \quad (1)$$

where,

$$\alpha_k = \frac{V_k}{V_{total}} \quad (2)$$

providing that the following condition is met,

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k = 0 \quad (3)$$

the subscript k demonstrates the phase indicator in the above equations.

x-momentum:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho u v)}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) + A u + \rho g \beta \cos \theta (T - T_m) \quad (4)$$

y-momentum:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u v)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v v)}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) + A v + \rho g \beta \sin \theta (T - T_m) \quad (5)$$

Energy:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho C_p T)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u C_p T)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v C_p T)}{\partial y} = + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) - S_T \quad (6)$$

where,

$$S_T = \frac{\partial(\rho \Delta H)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u \Delta H)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v \Delta H)}{\partial y} \quad (7)$$

in which ΔH represents the instantaneous change in latent heat.

In the momentum equations, the porosity function which is introduced by Brent et al. is as follows [31]:

$$A = -C \frac{(1 - \gamma)^2}{\gamma^3 + \epsilon} \quad (8)$$

In the previous equation, C and ϵ are two dimensionless constants defined as the mushy zone parameter (5×10^6) and a small-scale number (10^{-3}) that refrains from being divided by zero, respectively. A description of the liquid fraction, γ , follows:

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} 0 & T \leq T_s \\ \frac{T - T_s}{T_l - T_s} & T_s < T < T_l \\ 1 & T \geq T_l \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

For both the PCM and the water, the momentum and energy equations are solved at the same time. Meanwhile, for water, A and S_T are zero. A finite volume method is used to discretize momentum equations using a second-order upwind scheme, while a first-order upwind scheme

Table 1
The thermophysical properties of water and oleic acid.

Materials	$C_p(\frac{kJ}{kg \times K})$	$k(\frac{W}{m \times K})$	$\mu(\frac{kg}{m \times s})$	$h_{sf}(\frac{kJ}{kg})$	$\rho(\frac{kg}{m^3})$	$T_m(^{\circ}C)$	References
Oleic acid	2.15	0.24	0.003	80.6	850	13–14	[25,26]
Water	4.182	0.6	0.001003	—	998.2	—	[27,28]

Fig. 2. Numerical comparison between results reported by Kamkari and Amlashi [32] and the numerical model developed in the current study.

is used to discretize energy equations. In addition, momentum and continuity equations are coupled using the PISO algorithm. Iteratively solving the conservation equations, checking for convergence of velocity, pressure, and temperature fields in accordance with the convergence criterion of 10^{-6} , 10^{-6} , and 10^{-8} is carried out for each iteration.

2.3. Simulation validation

The numerical model is validated using the simulation results reported by Kamkari and Amlashi [32] for the liquid fraction and maximum velocity at the inclination angle of 45° . In the simulations, the geometry is a rectangular enclosure ($5\text{ cm} \times 12\text{ cm}$), with the side wall exposed to a constant temperature of 70°C and PCM temperature starting at 25°C . In this regard, the physical model used in Kamkari and Amlashi [32] is similar to the rectangular enclosure used in current research but with different dimensions and warmed wall temperature. As shown in Fig. 2, there is an accurate match between the available and simulated data. It is also worth noting present study simulated by a system with processor Intel Core i7 2.4 GHz and 8 GB RAM memory took approximately 6 h for inclined enclosure and 30 h for combined system.

3. Independence analysis

3.1. Grid independency study

The number of grid size impacts on melting fraction outcomes is estimated by using various grid sizes, including 25×20 , 50×40 , 66×50 , and 75×60 . The initial temperature of the water and oleic acid are considered 10°C , and the right wall is exposed to the constant temperature of 60°C . Fig. 3 shows the melting fraction for specified grid sizes during the melting process. Accordingly, the 66×50 grid size is chosen for

Fig. 3. The study of grid independency on melting fraction for the combined system of 50% water and 50% oleic acid.

Fig. 4. The study of time independency on melting fraction for the combined system of 50% water and 50% oleic acid.

subsequent calculation by comparing melting fractions of the four grid sizes.

3.2. Time step independency study

An analysis of time step independence for 66×50 grid size is shown in Fig. 4 by using three different time steps. A difference of less than 5%

Fig. 5. The melt fraction of oleic acid at different inclination angles in the enclosure.

is found between the melting fraction average for time steps of 0.01 and 0.005 s.

4. Results and discussion

One of the economical ways to improve the TES performance is to benefit inclined enclosure compared to using nanoparticles, metal foams, and fins due to its lower cost. At first, the melting process of oleic acid as a PCM in an inclined rectangular enclosure is investigated. In this analysis, the aim is to find the optimum inclination angle for the enclosure to attain the maximum rate of energy storage. Then, the en-

Fig. 6. The amount of energy storage at different inclination angles in the enclosure.

ergy storage method with the aid of auxiliary fluid is introduced and analyzed. Eventually, the average velocity of moving fluid and the energy storage rate of the TES system with auxiliary fluid is compared to the inclined system.

4.1. Inclined TES system analysis

Changing the inclination angle affects the melting of PCM in the enclosure, which consequently changes the rate of energy storage. The inclination of 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75°, and 90° are selected, and the melting and temperature contours are shown in Figs. A1-A7 of the Ap-

Fig. 7. The energy storage rate of oleic acid at different inclination angles in the enclosure.

Fig. 8. The melt fraction of oleic acid in the combined system (50% water and 50% oleic acid) and the optimal case of the inclined system (inclination of 30).

Fig. 10. The amount of energy storage in the combined system (50% water and 50% oleic acid) and the optimal case of the inclined system (inclination of 30).

Fig. 9. The average velocity of moving fluid in the combined system (50% water and 50% oleic acid) and optimal case of inclined system (inclination of 30).

pendix. Melt fraction at different times up to the end of the melting process is shown in Fig. 5. At the beginning of the melting process, all the inclination angles have almost the same melting rate because conduction is the dominant heat transfer mode. However, the convection heat transfer mode becomes prevalent with time, and the effect of the angle change becomes visible. Thermal plumes formed between two neighbor counter-rotating convection partitions cause melting in inclined enclosures to have a concave interface. As this plume carries the hot liquid from the heated wall to the interface, it accelerates the melting process. Interface waviness is caused by thermal plumes contacting the interface. The small vortical flow structures become larger as the liquid fraction increases. The inclination of 30°, 45°, and 60° accelerate the melting process more than the other inclinations, while the inclination of 0° has a longer melting time. Therefore, the melting rate can be improved by inclining the rectangular enclosure in specific inclinations. Also, Fig. 6 demonstrates the amount of energy that can be

stored for various inclinations during the melting process. It is observed that energy is stored faster in oleic acid at 15°, 30°, and 45° inclination angles.

To determine the optimal inclination angle, the energy storage rate at each inclination is calculated, and the maximum energy storage rate, which occurs at the inclination of 30°, is equal to 0.161983 kW/kg. Fig. 7 represents the energy storage rate in PCM at different inclination angles.

4.2. Combined TES systems analysis

In the combined system, water is used as an auxiliary fluid in direct contact with oleic acid in the enclosure. The combined TES systems are designed to use the density difference of two materials and strengthen the buoyancy force. During the melting process of oleic acid in the combined system shown in Fig. A8, water takes the melted oleic acid place, and oleic acid moves to the upper part of the enclosure due to its lower density than water. The details of the melting process of the combined system were discussed in Mehrjardi et al. [23]. The melting time of oleic acid in the combined system is 321.62 s, which shows an improvement compared to the optimal case of the inclined system (inclination of 30°), which lasted 898 s. Also, the melt fraction of the combined system with the optimal case of the inclined system is shown in Fig. 8, which exhibits the improvement of the melting performance of oleic acid when convection is the dominant mode of heat transfer.

Also, for a better understanding, the average velocity of moving fluid/fluids at different times is plotted in Fig. 9. The average velocity of fluids in the combined system is 0.0037 m/s, and for the moving fluid in the optimal case of inclined system is 0.00068 m/s, which indicates the intensity of convection heat transfer (5.44 times the optimal case of inclined system) in the combined system.

In addition, the amount of energy stored in the combined system with the optimal ureter of the inclined system is displayed in Fig. 10. The energy storage increase is higher in the combined system with a higher gradient. For a detailed analysis, the energy storage rate is shown in Fig. 11 to compare better the combined system and the optimal case of the inclined system. The energy storage rate in the combined system and the optimal case of the inclined system are 0.299136 kW/kg and 0.161983 kW/kg, respectively. The energy storage rate in the combined system is almost twice that of the inclined system. Also, the energy stor-

Fig. 11. The energy storage rate in the combined system (50% water and 50% oleic acid) and the optimal case of inclined system (inclination of 30°).

age rate in the PCM of the combined system is 0.376812 kW/kg, which is 2.33 times the energy storage rate in the PCM of the inclined system.

As a result, using water as an auxiliary fluid, a low-priced and accessible material, is a better enhancement method than the inclined enclosure method and other heat transfer improvements methods, such as nanoparticles and fins. Moreover, in the auxiliary fluid method, since water and oleic acid did not solve each other at the end of the melting process, water and oleic acid are entirely separated from each other. Consequently, the combined system should be designed to return to the initial state after the solidification of oleic acid by rotating the enclosure. Meanwhile, a 1 kg combined system includes 50% water and 50% oleic acid, which generate about 130 kJ energy in a complete cycle according to Fig. 6. This amount of energy is equal to adiabatic burning of 2.7 g of natural gas [33]. Also, it is worth noting 2.7 g natural gas emits 7.8 g CO₂ in stoichiometric reaction So, 1 kg of combined system in a complete cycle can prevent emissions of 7.8 g CO₂ instead of using natural gas.

5. Conclusions

In the present research, a comparison between the combined system and the inclined systems has been investigated. The combined system is defined as improving heat transfer by using an auxiliary fluid in direct contact with the PCM. The density difference between the two materials accelerates the melting process. Here are some of the main results obtained:

- In inclined enclosures, the inclination of 30° is the optimal angle, where the energy storage rate is 0.161983 kW/kg. According to the sizes of the designed chamber, the angles of 15°, 30°, and 45° have a higher stored energy rate than other angles.
- The energy storage rate in the combined system is equal to 0.299136 kW/kg, which is approximately 1.85 times higher energy storage rate in the inclined system (inclination of 30°).
- The energy storage rate of oleic acid in the combined system is 2.33 times the energy storage rate of the inclined system, which is a secure method due to the low cost of using water as an auxiliary fluid.
- The insolubility of water and oleic acid in each other is a strong point for the combined system because it can be returned to the initial state at the end of the melting process by solidifying the oleic acid and then rotating the enclosure to use in repeatable cycles.
- Changing the volume ratio of water and oleic acid, using other immiscible auxiliary fluids instead of water with a higher density than water, can be an essential topic to be studied in future research. [Appendix A, Eqn \(1\)-\(9\)](#).

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Appendix A

Fig. A1. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 0° in the enclosure.

Fig. A2. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 15° in the enclosure.

Fig. A3. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 30° in the enclosure.

Fig. A4. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 45° in the enclosure.

Fig. A5. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 60° in the enclosure.

Fig. A6. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 75° in the enclosure.

Fig. A7. The liquid fraction and temperature contours of oleic acid at the inclination of 90° in the enclosure.

Fig. A8. The liquid fraction, volume fraction of oleic acid, and temperature contours in the combine system (50% water and 50% oleic acid).

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